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A STUDY ON SOCIAL MEDIA ADDICTION AMONG YOUTH OF GUJARAT USING FACTOR ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This research is on the addition of social media among the youth of Gujarat. A questionnaire was made on google forms for collecting data. Convenience and snowball sampling technique was used as the data was collected by just sending google forms to the valid population. The valid population includes people having age between 15 and 25 and must be from Gujarat state as the research is limited to the youth of Gujarat state only. A sample of 253 people of Gujarat was taken. 4 responses were not taken in the analysis as they are not using social media. Factor analysis was run to the data of 248 responses on SPSS. Fourteen statements were classified into four factors according to factor loadings.

Keywords: Factor analysis, Social media, Youth, Gujarat

1. INTRODUCTION

A habit does not take too much time to convert into an addiction. The youth is extremely unaware of this fact. Once a person is addicted to anything, then it becomes difficult for them to live without a certain amount of that thing by which he is addicted.

This research was aimed at the effect on the behavior and performance of the youth of Gujarat due to the addiction to social media. The word Addiction refers to over-usage. Addiction refers not only to harmful and physical things like cigarettes, drugs, alcohol, or any other. But, it refers to over usage of anything. E.g. Playing too many games on mobile, watching too many movies/series. Just like that using social media for more than a certain limit is also called addiction to social media.

There is a very thin line between habit and addiction. People of today don't know the difference between these two. When any habit becomes a need for a person, it is no more habit. It becomes an addiction. They start smoking cigarettes just for enjoyment and that enjoyment becomes a habit and then it turns into an addiction. Just like that people start social media apps for being in contact with their friends, family members, and colleagues but it becomes a habit after start using them and like the time it becomes an addiction. Due to over usage of social media and seating the whole time holding a mobile phone in hands using social media alters the behavior and performance of a person. Sometimes, a person starts becoming weaker in academics, short

temper, neglecting important works, lack of sleep, mental absence, and many others can be the effects of over usage of social media. Mostly, all these problems are seen in youth, that is why the youth of Gujarat having ages between 15 and 25 is considered in this research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Mahamid & Berte (2019) made an attempt to examine the concept of geographical differences related to living in a military occupied area and try to understand the patterns of maladaptive addiction of social media in young adults. This study included 744 students of An- Najah National University of Palestine residents in occupied West Bank of Palestine. This study concluded that in geopolitical area high and few opportunities for leisure activities, open socialization are the main reasons of heightened vulnerability to an addiction as it is continual available, easy access and give imaginary satisfaction feeling for youth. This study also indicate that social media addiction may come at a high price for developing adults lack of social skills and from the fantasy of social media they are unable to discern reality and creating habits of to be formative in their adulthood.

Hou et. al (2019) examined the relations of social media addiction to college student's mental health and academic performance. Also investigated the role of self-esteem as a mediator for the relations and further examined the effectiveness of an intervention in reducing social media addiction and social media's adverse outcomes. This study used a two- stage self help intervention program with the help of 38 college students who meets the criteria of social media addiction to receive the intervention. This study concluded based on original findings that contribution in experimental database on social media addiction and they have both theoretical and practical implications.

Longobardi et. al (2020) examined the relation between Instagram popularity and subjective happiness, and investigate the mediating roles of cyber victimization and social media addiction. The study collects a sample of 345 middle school students who reported having an active Instagram account. A followers count showed a negative and indirect effect on subjective happiness via an increase in social media addiction and exposure to cyber victimization. Findings of this study indicate that when an adolescents become more popular on Instagram, it increases the risk that they develop a behavior addiction to Instagram use, and they also experience cyber aggression, that will in turn may have a negative impact on their psychological well-being. Adolescents whose activity on Instagram is more passive, and less dominated by social media, may be have less exposure to these negative consequences.

Veronica & Samuel (2015) concluded that addiction is caused by different degrees of physical, mental, circumstantial, and emotional factors. In addiction the incentive recognition is not longer felt, and the addiction continues to become larger and withdrawal from this becomes painstaking as well as unsuccessful for the individual and his family. The study also indicates that various reasons affect the well-being of adolescents and some of them being, the objectives and the goals of the adolescent being smashed, Loss of Parental relationship, Disrupted social media addiction and the reason and effects that surge social, mental, and behavioral among adolescents.

Arslan et. al (2021) examined a interpersonal relationships, Fading Social and cultural values, subjection to an unhealthy environment. The present study made an attempt to understand

moderated mediation model in which college belongingness mediated the relationship between coronavirus anxiety, psychological adjustment and this mediation effect was moderated by social media addiction. A total of 315 undergraduate students selected as participant in this study. The results of the study indicated that college belongingness partially mediated the relationship between coronavirus anxiety and psychological adjustment. The mediating part from coronavirus anxiety to college belongingness was moderated by social media addiction. In comparison with the high level of social media addiction, coronavirus anxiety had a stronger predictive effect college belongingness under the low and moderate levels of social media addiction condition. This study points out that college belongingness is a potential mechanism explaining how coronavirus anxiety is related to psychological adjustment and that this relation may depend on the levels.

Grau et. al (2019) examined the phenomenon of social media addiction among student Millennials. This study used the consumption continuum as a theoretical framework. This study used a “media deprivation” methodology including both qualitative and quantitative measures. The study reveal that social media may exist in some respondents in a near addiction phase or according to the consumption continuum framework. This study have the limitation that the sample is small, this paper is an exploratory study of social media addiction among Millennials. This paper explores the idea of social media addiction and examined the role that marketing plays in perpetuating social media addiction.

Kant (2020) has done study on the students of Central University of South Bihar, Gaya, India. In this study, 200 students participated from the School of Education and School of Law & Governance. Among the participants 41% were female and 59% were male. Most of participants were Facebook and WhatsApp users. After going through the research, it was concluded that among the participants most of them were addicted to social media. Most of the participants didn't have an addiction to social media. Social Media Addiction was not significantly different based on gender, but male students were more addicted to social media than females. As more expansion of Internet availability, rural students were more addicted in comparison to urban students.

Ünal (2020) investigate the social media addiction of the New Media and Journalism students, who were heavy users of new media tools, at Üsküdar University. The sample size of the research consists of 85 students from New Media and Journalism Department. The research was analyzed using a comparative survey model, with the data collected from Social Media Addiction Scale and social media addiction of students were explored in terms of various demographic variables. The study found that Social media addiction increases as the daily time spent increases, Students sharing photos on social media by applying filter/makeup were found to be more addicted regarding the mood modification aspect. Students use social media when they wake up in the morning, during the day, and before bed, New Media and Journalism students' Instagram use is high, followed by students using Twitter the more.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

- What variables cause differing levels of addiction in social media use?
- To know the level of social media(SM) addiction among the youth of Gujarat.

- Impact of social media on performance in education.
- Impact of Social media on the Behavior of Youth.

3.2 DATA COLLECTION METHOD

- The convenience and Snowball sampling methods were used for the collection of data.
- A questionnaire on Google forms was made containing basic information and fourteen different statements related to social media.
- Information was collected only through Google forms by sharing it on WhatsApp.
- The data collected was restricted to Gujarat state and having ages between 15 and 25 years only.

3.3 QUESTIONNAIRE

- Fourteen statements consisting of a Likert scale of five were used to measure social media addiction among youth.
- Responses were set ranged from Strongly agree (1) to Strongly disagree (5).
- All statements were classified under three headings in the questionnaire. Each heading is itself a question.

The following table shows all the fourteen statements included in the questionnaire.

Time and Importance are given to social media

- I use social media longer than intended
- I find life to be boring without social media
- I could pass several days without feeling the need to use social media
- I would not care about time while using social media
- I feel my social media usage has increased significantly since I began using them

Change in behavior due to the use of social media

- I get irritated when someone interrupts me when I am using social media
- I would be upset if I had to cut down the amount of time I spend using social media
- I find myself thinking about what happened in social media when I am away from them
- I would not respond to others while I am using social media

The effect in routine life

- I neglect my work because of my usage of social media
- I find it difficult to sleep shortly after using social media
- My family frequently complain of my involvement with social media
- My result has fallen because of my social media usage
- I would not pay attention to other work while using social media

3.4 SAMPLE

- A sample of 253 respondents was taken for analysis from different districts of Gujarat.

- Out of 253, 5 respondents were not using social media. Therefore, they were removed at the time of analysis.

4. ANALYSIS

- Factors analysis was run on SPSS.
- Four factors were formed by SPSS according to Factor Loadings.
- Classification of factor wise statements is as under:

Factor 1:

- 1) I would not pay attention to other work while using social media
- 2) I find it difficult to sleep shortly after using social media
- 3) My result has fallen because of my social media usage
- 4) I neglect my work because of my usage of social media
- 5) My family frequently complain of my involvement with social media

Factor 2:

- 1) I would be upset if I had to cut down the amount of time I spend using social media
- 2) I find myself thinking about what happened in social media when I am away from them
- 3) I would not respond to others while I am using social media
- 4) I get irritated when someone interrupts me when I am using social media

Factor 3:

- 1) I feel my social media usage has increased significantly since I began using them
- 2) I find life to be boring without social media
- 3) I use social media longer than intended
- 4) I would not care about time while using social media

Factor 4:

- 1) I could pass several days without feeling the need to use social media

Names were given to factors as under

- **Factor 1:** Effect in routine life
- **Factor 2:** Change in behavior due to use of social media (SM)
- **Factor 3:** Time and importance are given to social media (SM)
- **Factor 4:** Dependency on social media (SM)

5. GRAPHS AND CHARTS

5.1 Gender Chart

Out of the total 253 respondents, 58.1% were males whereas the remaining 41.9% were females. The total number of males were 147 and females were 106.

5.2 Age Chart

Youth having age between 15 to 25 were taken in the study. Out of a total of 253 responses, the maximum number of respondents were having age 23 years. The total number of

5.4 Do you use social media?

Out of a total of 253 respondents, 98% were using social media. The number of which is 248. Only 5 people were not using social media, which is only 2% of total responses. Though the sample is too small, the ratio of people using social media to people not using social media is dangerous. This ratio is 100:1, which shows that only 1 out of 100 people do not use social media. This leads to a serious problem if social media become an addiction among the youth of people. This may cause serious problems like low concentration, a decrease in mental growth, weird behavior, etc.

5.5 Which social media do you use?

The most used app when the research was made was WhatsApp, YouTube, and Instagram. 245 out of 253 were using WhatsApp which is 98.8% of the total responses received. After that YouTube is in 2nd place. 229 people use YouTube out of total responses which are 92.3%. Instagram is 3rd most used app. 219 out of total respondents use this app which is 88.3%. Facebook and Telegram users are also more than 50%. Users of other apps like Quora, LinkedIn, Twitter, and Snapchat are below 50%. Users of Tiktok are only 4% according to the study.

5.6 Which social media do you use most?

Here, the most used app refers to time spent on a particular app. In this, WhatsApp is the most used app on which 39.9% of people spent their time. WhatsApp is the most popular app. Instagram is the second popular app according to the study. 33.9% of people use Instagram the most. The third popular app is YouTube, users of which are 19.4%. All other apps are used by less than 5% of total respondents

5.7 Hours Spent Using Social Media per Day

Most people do not spend much time on social media. This is a good sign. People spending less than 2 hours per day on social media are 81 out of a total of 253 which is 32.7%. People

spending 2-4 hours on social media are 99 which is 39.9%. 17.3% of people spend 4-6 hours daily on social media, the number of which is 43. Less than 10% of people spent more than 6 hours on social media which is good for the development of youth.

5.8 Time and Importance are given to social media

1. 81 out of 253 agree that they use SM longer than intended. Against this, 44 disagree on over usage of SM. 71 are neutral on this statement.
2. 69 people think life to be boring without SM, 58 people disagree on this. Whereas 64 people are neutral on this.
3. 92 respondents agree that they could pass several days without using SM. Whereas 39 people strongly agree. Very few disagree with this statement. The number of disagreeing people is only 29. The number of people who are neutral on this is 75.
4. 84 people disagree whereas only 41 agree on the statement of not caring about time while using SM. 65 people remain neutral.
5. 92 people feel that their SM usage has increased since they started using them. 43 people strongly agree whereas 66 people are neutral on this statement. 34 people disagree with the statement.

5.9 Change in behavior due to the use of social media

1. 60 people accept that they get irritated when someone interrupts them while using SM. 77 disagree with this statement whereas 55 are neutral.
2. 101 out of total responses disagree with the statement that they would be upset if the time of using SM is to cut down. 36 people strongly disagree. 48 are neutral whereas 45 people agree and 18 people strongly agree with this statement.
3. 69 respondents disagree that they think about what happened in SM when they are away from it. 63 agree whereas 57 remain neutral on this statement. 40 people strongly disagree with this.
4. 104 people disagree whereas only 51 agree on the statement of not responding to others while using SM. 38 people remain neutral whereas 36 people agree to this.

5.10 The effect in routine life

1. 93 people out of a total of 253 disagree that they neglect their work because of their usage of SM. 48 strongly disagree whereas 47 remain neutral and 43 people agree with this statement.
2. 83 respondents disagree with the statement that they face difficulties sleeping shortly after using SM. Against this, 59 people agree with the statement. 52 respondents remain neutral whereas 40 strongly disagree with the statement.
3. 55 accepts that their family frequently complaints about their involvement in SM. 56 remain neutral but 77 disagree that their family complaints about involvement in SM. 31 strongly disagree whereas 29 strongly agree with the statement.
4. 90 people disagree whereas only 36 agree with the statement that their results have fallen because of their usage of SM. 57 people strongly disagree and 48 remain neutral whereas only 17 people strongly agree with the statement.
5. 92 people disagree that they would not pay attention to other work while using SM. Against this, 46 agree with the statement. 41 people remain neutral and 45 people strongly disagree with the statement.

5.11 Can you live without social media?

The last question was asked to know the level of dependency on SM. In that, the answer of 117 people (which is almost 50%) was “YES”. 97 people (39.1%) people replied “NO” to the question. This means that they cannot live without SM. 34 people answered “MAYBE”. It means they are not sure whether they can live without SM or not.

6. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

6.1 Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.887	42.051	42.051	5.887	42.051	42.051	3.666	26.184	26.184
2	1.444	10.315	52.366	1.444	10.315	52.366	2.684	19.170	45.354
3	1.252	8.946	61.312	1.252	8.946	61.312	2.204	15.741	61.095
4	1.075	7.679	68.991	1.075	7.679	68.991	1.105	7.896	68.991
5	.666	4.757	73.748						
6	.601	4.290	78.037						
7	.543	3.881	81.919						
8	.533	3.810	85.728						
9	.446	3.189	88.917						
10	.387	2.761	91.678						
11	.345	2.464	94.142						
12	.296	2.117	96.259						
13	.281	2.005	98.264						
14	.243	1.736	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The above table shows the total variance explained by each component i.e. statement. We can see that 68.991 % of the variance is explained by the four components. These components are nothing but the four factors in which all 14 statements will be classified. The Principal Component Analysis method was used in SPSS for factoring.

For the classification of statements into factors, the Varimax rotation method was used. The following table shows the classification of all statements into 4 factors.

6.2 Rotated Component Matrix

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
1. Not pay attention to other work	.814	.249	.158	
2. Difficult to sleep shortly	.784	.198		-.102
3. Result have fallen	.767	.231	.157	.132

4. Neglect work	.762	.245	.289	
5. Family frequently complain	.762	.196	.255	
6. Be upset if cut down the time	.218	.828	.212	
7. Thinking about what happened when away from them	.135	.813	.214	
8. Not respond to others	.435	.697		
9. Get irritated when someone interrupts	.387	.657	.132	
10. Usage has increased since began using	.134		.756	.222
11. Life to be boring		.299	.686	-.287
12. Use longer	.363		.685	
13. Not care of time	.287	.260	.613	.170
14. Pass days without feeling the need to use				.942
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.				
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.				
a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.				

We can see from the above 2 tables that factor 1 contributes the most in explaining the total variance. And the name given to Factor 1 is “Effect in routine life”. This means that addiction to social media affects the youth. These effects are (i) not paying attention to other works while using SM (ii) difficult to sleep shortly after using SM (iii) falling of result (iv) neglecting of work (v) family frequently complaining of involvement with SM etc.

Factor 2 does not contribute as much as Factors 1. This means that due to the use of SM, there is no significant change in youth’s behavior. It includes (i) be upset if cut down the time of use of SM (ii) thinking about SM when away from them (iii) not respond to others (iv) get irritated when someone interrupts.

Factor 3 refers to give time and importance to the SM. This includes (i) usage of SM is increased (ii) finding life boring without SM (iii) using SM longer than intended (iv) Not caring of time while using SM.

As factor 4 explains dependency on SM. Most people can pass days without feeling the need to use social media.

7. LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

- The sample includes youth of having age between 15 and 25 only.
- The sample collected is limited to Gujarat state only.
- Convenience and snowball sampling method was used.

8. CONCLUSION

Out of total responses, 98% are using social media. Only 2% of total responses were not using social media. Though the sample is too small, the ratio of people using social media to people not using social media is dangerous. This ratio is 100:1, which shows that only 1 out of 100 people do not use social media. This leads to a serious problem if social media become an addiction among youth. This may cause serious problems like low concentration, a decrease in

mental growth, weird behavior, etc. Most of them do not spend much time on social media. This is a good sign. The percentage of people spending less than 2 hours per day on social media is 32.7%. People spending 2-4 hours on social media is 39.9%. 17.3% of people spend 4-6 hours daily on social media. Less than 10% of people are of those categories who spend more than 6 hours on social media which is good for the development of youth.

From the research conducted on the addiction of social media, we can conclude that the effects of social media are more in the routine life of people. This includes not paying attention to other works while using social media, difficulty to sleep shortly after using social media, family complaints of involvement with social media, falls result and neglecting work because of social media usage. This means that social media seriously affects the routine life of the youth. Though the sample size is too small, the results we got are very clear. Other factors are not that effective but still, they are serious. Those factors are change in behavior

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